

Integrating Structural Biology

Instruct-ULTRA

WP7 – Streamlining Access Procedures for Pioneering Structural Biology Methods

Lead Beneficiaries: P10 - CNRS

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Deliverable D7.2: Standardised workflows for integrative sample preparation methods for structural biology in cells

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Project objective

The objective is to integrate sample preparation methods for structural biology in cells.

Executive summary

Performing structural studies in a cellular context provides a view and understanding of proteins that cannot be obtained on purified samples in simple aqueous environments. Interactions with cellular partners can be measured in the crowded, natural cellular environment that strongly influences the dynamics, affinities and kinetics of proteins and their interactions. Proteins also span a spectrum of foldedness, from well-folded to intrinsically disordered, and these states are also affected strongly by the cellular *milieu*.

In the first NMR-focused part of this work package, partner P12 (CIRMMP) developed and optimised an NMR bioreactor system to standardise the workflow of real-time in-cell NMR applications. Different configurations were tested for supporting human cells in biocompatible hydrogels. A workflow was optimised, allowing up to ~72 hours of NMR experiments with high cell viability, and applied to observe real-time protein-ligand interactions. P10 (CNRS Grenoble) extended the field of application of in-cell NMR to large proteins (a challenging area for NMR) using $^{13}\text{CH}_3$ specific isotopic labelling. They successfully demonstrated this strategy on an 82 kDa target in bacterial cells and developed new $^{13}\text{CH}_3$ -labelling protocols to extend its application to eukaryotic cells at the limit of this method. P13 (UU) also developed labeling approaches, for parallel investigations of macromolecular complexes involving intrinsically disordered proteins, by NMR and small angle scattering (SAS) *in vitro* and for studies of these complexes by in-cell NMR. They established a workflow permitting collection, from the same sample, of both local structural

information by NMR and overall shape information (demonstrated on a 120 kDa IDP-complex). This was further extended to interactions of IDPs by in-cell NMR. In the second focus of this work package, P10 (CNRS Strasbourg) established a workflow based on an in-cell CRISPR/Cas9 methodology. The methodology permits purification of macromolecular complexes directly from endogenous sources, and labelling of individual proteins and macromolecular complexes with fluorescent reporter tags for imaging applications in both electron and light microscopy.

Deliverable D7.2: Standardised workflows for integrative sample preparation methods for structural biology in cells

Partner P13 (UU) focussed their efforts on the characterisation of complexes formed by intrinsically disordered proteins (IDPs) both in cells and *in vitro*. The importance of such complexes in regulating cell biology and the requirement for integrative structural approaches for their characterisation has been recognised in recent years. Yet, the structural characterisation of protein complexes involving IDPs remains challenging - in particular for large, multi-subunit complexes and for characterisation of such complexes in the cellular environment. Sample preparation methods were tested for two model IDP systems that form large and dynamic complexes. One system (~125 kDa complex) was tested *in vitro* to allow parallel investigation by NMR, cross-linking and native mass spectrometry, as well as Small-Angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS) and Small-Angle Neutron Scattering (SANS).

A differential deuteration labelling protocol was chosen to allow simultaneous NMR and SANS investigation of the full complex in a quantitative manner. The second system was tested in-cell, using the cellular abundance of the binding target to form a highly dynamic complex (~200 kDa) with the IDP. In this case, ^{15}N isotope-labelling was sufficient for detection of the complex. Further work on optimising the preparation for parallel solution and solid-state NMR in-cell investigations and combination with in-cell crosslinking mass spectrometry is in progress.

Figure 1. (a) Parallel quantitative investigation by NMR and SAXS/SANS of the large and dynamic complex formed by histone chaperone APLF and the histone octamer. (b) In-cell NMR observation of a chromatin binding protein demonstrating high disorder in the complex with cellular chromatin.

Partner P10 (CNRS Grenoble) focused their efforts on the use of $^{13}\text{CH}_3$ probes specifically introduced in perdeuterated proteins in order to extend the field of application of in cell NMR to large proteins. In-cell NMR is used as a cellular structural approach to characterise macromolecular interactions and functions in a physiological environment. However, the

applications of in-cell NMR have, so far, been mostly restricted to small proteins or very flexible protein segments, such as intrinsically disordered proteins (IDPs). In-cell NMR studies of large and well-folded proteins are limited by the slow overall tumbling of large objects in overcrowded cellular environment. In a proof-of-principle study, Malate Synthase G (MSG; 82 kDa) was chosen as it is widely used as a model for NMR development. MSG, labelled on isoleucine-d1 methyl position, was expressed in *E. coli* cells and purified to acquire a reference spectrum. We have developed our protocol in order to prepare optimised sample and to acquire in few minutes 2D NMR spectra of the 82 kDa MSG protein in *E. coli* cells (See panel A of Fig. 2).

Figure 2. (A) Superimposition of *in vivo* (black) and *in vitro* (red) methyl TROSY spectra of MSG (82 kDa) specifically labelled on Isoleucine-d1 methyl probes; (B) 2D methyl TROSY spectra of ATP binding domain of the human hsp90 (28 kDa) expressed in HEK cells and specifically labelled on Met- and Thr-g methyl groups.

Contrary to the use of ^{15}N -labelling (for which ^{15}N - ^1H signals of free amino acids are not *NMR-visible* due to the fast exchange of these protons with solvent) $^{13}\text{CH}_3$ -labelling involves presence in cells of a significant level of labelled metabolites with non-exchangeable protons covalently bound to ^{13}C atoms. Those labelled metabolites give rise to a background signal, hampering the identification of the labelled protein NMR resonances. This background signal cannot be completely suppressed by the subtraction of a reference spectrum. Therefore, we have investigated the limit of the methods as a function of the expression level of the target protein. We have determined that a level of expression higher than c.a. 20 mg/L of culture is required for analysis of the labelled protein by in cell CH_3 -NMR.

Finally, in order to extend the applicability of in cell CH_3 -NMR to eukaryotic protein targets, we have developed new precursors and protocols to label any types of methyl groups in proteins expressed in insect (sf9) and human (HEK) cells (See panel B of Figure 2). Further work to characterise human proteins by in cell CH_3 -NMR is in progress.

Partner 10 (CNRS Strasbourg), in collaboration with the TacGene platform (JP Concordet, MNHN Paris), has continued the development of a pipeline for the purification of macromolecular complexes from endogenous sources. A cell line whose genome can be engineered with the CRISPR/Cas9 technology, and which can be easily grown in suspension, was selected. The target protein was produced under the control of its natural promoter and the resulting complexes were authentic (no problems of stoichiometry, post translation modifications (PTMs), missing components) but yield was limited by the natural abundance of the complex. The pipeline included the following steps: (i) establishment of K562 knocked-in cell lines in which a subunit of the target assembly has been fused to the

FLAG affinity tag, (ii) validation of selected clones, (iii) large scale suspension cultures, and (iv) affinity purification of the target complex. As proof of concept, the XPB subunit of the transcription/DNA repair factor TFIIH was tagged with the FLAG peptide (Figure 3). Ongoing and future experiments focus on the evaluation of the Strep and the green fluorescent protein (GFP) tags for purification instead of the FLAG tag and protocol validation.

In parallel, Partner 10 (CNRS Strasbourg) has also worked on the implementation and standardisation of procedures for labelling complexes in cells for imaging (live cell confocal and super resolution microscopy). A knocked in cell line where the XPB subunit of the transcription/DNA repair complex was labelled with the mEOS2 GFP derivative was obtained and is being evaluated. The use of sortase-mediated transpeptidation for site-specific protein labelling of recombinant Fabs (antigen-binding fragments) or nanmCherry nanobodies. Delivery of validated protocols is expected in 6-9 months.

Figure 3. Genome editing technologies to facilitate the purification of endogenous complexes.

(A) Purification of multiprotein complexes via affinity tagging is optimal when expression of the bait protein is specified by its natural genomic context. A genome-editing-based approach to tag endogenous genes and purify native complexes from human cells to near homogeneity was implemented (in collaboration with the TacGene Platform). **(B)** As proof of principle the gene encoding the XPB subunit of the transcription/DNA repair factor was tagged with a FLAG peptide in K562 cells and a purification from large scale suspension culture was setup.

Partner P12 (CIRMMP) focussed their efforts on the development and optimisation of an NMR bioreactor system for in-cell NMR applications. The device consists of a flow NMR device adapted to allow human cells to be maintained in the NMR spectrometer in a viable and metabolically stable state for prolonged periods of time, by providing a continuous flow of fresh nutrients. Specifically, for in-cell NMR applications that require a high density of cells in the NMR active volume, CIRMMP has tested and implemented different bioreactor setups where cells are embedded in bio-compatible gel matrices. Several matrices have been tested at various densities of hydrogel and embedded cell numbers, including agarose

threads, alginate beads and mixed alginate-gelatine materials. Cell viability was measured by Trypan blue staining at increasing times of active flow (Fig. 4) and was correlated with metabolic activity measured by MTT assay. Simultaneously, concentrations of abundant metabolites in the collected outflow were measured by 1D NMR and were correlated with signal intensities in the 1D NMR spectra collected directly on the cells.

Agarose threads were then employed to demonstrate the application of the NMR bioreactor to monitor structural changes of an intracellular protein of interest, in real time, in response to external stimuli. Specifically, ligand binding to the second isoform of carbonic anhydrase was monitored by 1D ^1H NMR in human cells, while the formation of an intramolecular disulphide bond of superoxide dismutase 1 in response to an external molecule was monitored by 2D ^1H - ^{15}N correlation NMR in human cells. Time-resolved data was collected over the course of up to ~72 hours, during which changes in the in-cell NMR spectra were observed over timescales ranging from minutes to several hours. Data analysis to obtain the concentration profiles of the intracellular species of interest was performed in a semi-automated way by a multivariate curve resolution algorithm.

Work in progress is focusing on the implementation of the current bioreactor design, with the aim of streamlining the workflow to allow users to access the new technology. In the next step, access to the bioreactor platform will be tested by real users through an open call.

Further development of the NMR bioreactor is also ongoing, focusing on the optimisation of the properties of non-agarose hydrogels, and on its application to larger-scale ligand screenings by protein-observe in-cell NMR.

Figure 4. Trypan blue stain of HEK293T cells in agarose threads after incubation with medium flow (top row) and without medium flow (bottom row).

Test Access for New Technologies

Milestone 18 was achieved at the revised date of December 2019. This was an open call for projects with an integrative approach as use cases for sample preparation. Each of the technologies developed within D7.2 were invited to offer test access to an external user, in order to assess the new technology and further refine workflows. Three technologies were sufficiently advanced to offer test access (see table 1) and the call was advertised on the Instruct-ULTRA website.

Technology Offered	Lead scientist offering technology
In-Cell NMR in Grenoble	Jerome Boisbouvier (P10)
Bioreactor for time resolved in Cell NMR	Enrico Luchinat (P12)
Endogenous protein tagging for structural biology	Arnaud Poterszman (P10)

Table 1. Technology offered as part of Instruct-ULTRA Test Access to new sample preparation services for integrative approaches

Submissions were subject to a technical and peer review at the end of the call in January 2020, and three proposals were approved.

Approved test access projects

The three proposals approved for test access were initiated in February 2020, with preparations made and reagents ordered. Unfortunately, the lock-down of European laboratories during the COVID-19 pandemic has delayed the start of active research, however each project is planned to go ahead as soon as possible after laboratories reopen.

1. **In Cell NMR.** The eukaryotic cell labelling protocols of P10 have been offered within the WP7 open call for user projects, and a project of an SME (Dr Emily Crublet, NMR-Bio) has been approved for access. The access will be scheduled once the platform reopens after the current lockdown. The NMR ¹³C labelling protocols for large proteins developed in T7.2 by P10 will be transferred to any user upon request.
2. **Bioreactor for time resolved in Cell.** The in-cell Bioreactor technology of P12 has been offered within the WP7 open call for user projects and a project of a user (Matteo Pennestri, Bruker UK) has been approved for access. The access will be scheduled once the platform reopens after the current lockdown.
3. **Endogenous protein tagging for structural biology.** The CRISPR knock-in technology has been offered within the WP7 call for user projects and a project of Jan Bednar (Institute of Advanced Biotechnologies, Grenoble) has been approved for access. The access will be scheduled once the platform reopens after the current lockdown.

In addition, P10 is inviting test users for integrative studies of IDP-complexes. The access will be scheduled once the platform reopens after the current lockdown.

Publications for Task 7.2

Five manuscripts are in preparation.

One such manuscript submitted to *Methods in Molecular Biology*: Gene tagging with the CRISPR-Cas9 system to facilitate macromolecular complex purification. Sylvain Geny, Simon Pichard, Arnaud Poterszman, Jean-Paul Concordet.

Summary

Three Instruct-ULTRA partners (P10 – CNRS, P13 – UU and P12 – CIRMMP) have made significant advances in the development of methods for the preparation and analysis of proteins in cells and in real-time. Proof of concept experiments have been carried demonstrating the potential of the new methods. Three proposals for test access to the new technologies have been approved and are planned to begin after European laboratories re-open following COVID-19 restrictions. Once test access has been complete, the new sample preparation technologies will be offered within the Instruct-ERIC catalogue of services to be available to scientists across Europe. In addition, key findings and workflows will be published in scientific papers over the next year, which will allow wide dissemination of these significant research methods.